

Cost-Effective Federated Learning-Based Approach for SINR Prediction in Cellular-Connected UAVs

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Abstract—This study introduces a novel approach to empower cellular-connected Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) in predicting signal quality. The proposed prediction model leverages data collected by the UAVs, addressing privacy concerns and ensuring effectiveness, while taking into account the constraints of UAVs. A unique three-step approach is proposed, which integrates a detailed physical Ray-Tracing (RT) method, deep learning, and Federated Learning (FL) for continuous learning and field adaptation. A Dual Input Feature Fusion Convolutional Neural Network (DIFF-CNN) model is proposed, which is pretrained on RT data and fine-tuned using data collected by the UAVs via FL. The proposed model demonstrates superior performance and robustness to data sparsity compared to traditional machine learning algorithms. Notably, the model achieves a root mean squared error of 0.837 dB and an R-squared of 97.7% for SINR prediction after the fine-tuning step in the fixed-altitude scenario, but performance drops with uniform altitude distribution, highlighting the impact of flying height on fine-tuning. The research indicates that the proposed approach can enhance performance while reducing training rounds by 35% to 90%, thus mitigating FL overheads. Future research could explore efficiency gains by using different pretrained models tailored to specific flying heights.

Keywords—federated learning, unmanned aerial vehicle, convolutional neural network, ray-tracing, signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio

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1 Introduction

Wireless communication is a pivotal technology that enables a wide range of applications and services, including mobile networks, the Internet of Things, smart cities, and autonomous vehicles^[1-3]. Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) have emerged as a promising tool for improving the performance of wireless networks and enhancing the quality of human life. UAVs can function both as providers and consumers of wireless networks^[4-5]. Cellular-connected UAVs can utilize existing networks to support applications such as remote sensing, virtual reality, and item delivery^[4]. Nonetheless, the Air-Ground (AG) communication channel between a UAV and a Ground Base Station (GBS) is influenced by the environment in which the signals are propagated and the probability of line-of-sight (LoS) between UAV and GBS, which depends on the UAV's flying height^[4]. Furthermore, it is crucial to ensure 3D coverage for UAVs to provide quality services to the end-users and safety and control to the UAVs^[6-7]. Hence, it is critical for UAVs to be aware of the 3D signal quality of the cellular network in advance to autonomously optimize their operations and avoid “holes-in-the-sky” phenomenon.

UAVs, which are typically owned by different entities, can pose privacy and security issues with traditional Machine Learning (ML) due to data sharing. Federated Learning (FL) addresses privacy concerns by enabling UAVs to collaboratively train a global model without data sharing or transmission to a central server^[4,8]. Subsequently, UAVs can utilize the globally aggregated model to predict the network state, thereby optimizing their placement, trajectory planning, and data routing^[9-11]. However, as UAVs have energy and computational constraints, FL needs to be optimized to reduce the computation and communication overheads^[12-14].

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1.1 State of the Art and Prior Work

Cellular coverage awareness involves being able to predict the Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR), which should exceed a certain reliability threshold. The path loss model plays a crucial role in predicting the SINR as it describes how the signal power decays with distance and other environmental factors. Path loss models can be divided into two main approaches, i.e., measurement-based empirical models and simulation-based deterministic or stochastic models.

Based on field measurement, the characterization of AG was presented Ref. [15], indicating that path loss results closely align with the Flat-Earth Two-Ray (FE2R) model. However, The authors also discovered that multipath delays create more challenging channel conditions for AG. The authors Ref. [16] conducted field measurements in live LTE networks and found that as UAVs ascend, path loss decreases, approximating free-space propagation. They suggest using height-dependent models for efficient prediction in cellular-connected UAVs.

Ray-Tracing (RT) deterministic method simulates the propagation of radio waves in a given environment by tracing the paths of rays that reflect and diffract from different surfaces and objects^[17-18]. RT method can provide accurate and realistic path-loss results but require detailed information about the environment's geometry and material properties as well as significant computational resources, especially when the target area is large^[18-19]. A comparison between RT simulations and field measurements for UAV AG channel in a suburban type setting was presented Ref. [20]. While the agreement between measurements and RT simulations was generally good, it was less so at very low heights (1-10m) due to diffuse scattering. More recently Ref. [21], the authors investigated UAV in 6G communication in mountainous regions. They found that higher altitudes increase signal coverage but decrease channel capacity. Additionally, they noted that RT data and measurement data followed the same distribution.

Beyond empirical and simulation-based models, there is an increasing inclination towards employing ML models for predicting path loss and SINR in AG communications. Recent research tends to use RT data to train an ML model that is optimized using measurement data^[22-24]. The authors Ref. [22] proposed a deep neural network model, which is initially trained using extensive RT simulation data and subsequently optimized with a limited set of measurement data. This model incorporates factors such as path delay, carrier frequency, and reflection angle of non-line-of-sight (NLoS) paths. The predicted results exhibit a strong correlation with the validation set, which is derived from RT simulation and measurement data. However, the model does not consider the altitude of the UAV. A transfer learning framework to predict the channel

characteristics of unmeasured scenarios based on measured ones was proposed Ref. [23]. More recently Ref. [24], the authors propose an artificial neural network that uses RT simulation data for pretraining and measurement data for optimization training in agricultural scenarios. The model inputs are the propagation distance, the UAV height, and the carrier frequency. The results show that the proposed model is more accurate than traditional empirical models. However, it is limited to one transmitter and does not account for potential interference from other transmitters in the environment. FL was employed to construct a global model of outage probability Ref. [25]. This model, trained on UAV data, was utilized to enhance the path planning for UAVs. However, the study did not address the overheads associated with FL.

1.2 Contribution

To the best of our knowledge, there are no existing studies that jointly employ RT method and FL to construct a coverage prediction model for cellular-connected UAVs. In this study, our objective is to create a model that can predict the SINR at different heights and across a broad region using a three-step approach. The proposed approach combines detailed physical RT modeling, deep learning, and a pragmatic strategy for continuous learning and adaptation in the field using FL.

1. **RT Simulation:** We utilize the RT model based on the Shooting and Bouncing Rays (SBR) method^[26] to compute signal propagation paths between multiple GBSs and a receiver at arbitrary locations and altitudes in a region encompassing urban and suburban zones. This step involves the use of RT method to generate an offline dataset, containing features that are detached from the global coordinate system.
2. **Pretraining:** we propose a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model to be pretrained on the offline dataset to predict signal quality in the selected region to mitigate the computational costs associated with the SBR method and FL.
3. **Fine-tuning:** Each UAV gathers data about the network's condition at various locations during its flight. This data forms a unique local online dataset for each UAV, which is used to fine-tune the pretrained model using FL. We demonstrate that starting with a pretrained model in FL reduces both computational and communication costs by minimizing the number of global updates. As a result, the global model achieves high performance more efficiently compared to the conventional scenario where the global model is randomly initialized. Furthermore, this process allows the global model to adapt to specific altitudes, enhancing its predictive accuracy for different scenarios.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 outlines the system model. Section 3 details the proposed three steps approach. Section 4 presents both the simulation setup and the results of each step. Section 5 discusses the key findings and potential future work. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

2 System Model

In this study, we examine an outdoor environment, denoted as \mathcal{O} . This environment is characterized by its minimum coordinates $(X_{\min}, Y_{\min}, Z_{\min})$ and maximum coordinates $(X_{\max}, Y_{\max}, Z_{\max})$. The system under consideration, located within \mathcal{O} , comprises of J GBSs, each situated at distinct locations (x_j, y_j, z_j) , where $1 \leq j \leq J$. Additionally, the system includes a set of U UAVs, each positioned at different coordinates (x_u, y_u, H_u) , where $1 \leq u \leq U$. Each GBS transmits signal of power P_j that propagates through the environment and is received by a UAV. Figure 1 shows an example with one UAV and two GBSs, along with the propagation paths between them. The received signal power $S_{j,u}$ at the u^{th} UAV due to the j^{th} GBS can be expressed taking into account the propagation loss, antenna gains, and any interference and noise present in the system. $S_{j,u}$ can be represented as follows:

$$S_{j,u} = P_j G_j(\theta_j, \phi_j) G_u(\theta_u, \phi_u) PL_{j,u} \quad (1)$$

where $G_j(\theta_j, \phi_j)$ is the antenna gain of the j^{th} GBS in the direction of (θ_j, ϕ_j) , $G_u(\theta_u, \phi_u)$ is the antenna gain of the u^{th} UAV in the direction of (θ_u, ϕ_u) , θ_j and θ_u are the elevation angles, ϕ_j and ϕ_u are the azimuth angles, and $PL_{j,u}$ is the path loss between the j^{th} GBS and the u^{th} UAV.

To address interference, we assume that UAVs either use orthogonal time-frequency resources, thereby avoiding mutual interference, or employ advanced multiple access schemes such as Orthogonal Multiple Access (OMA) or Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA). In OMA, UAVs are allocated separate time or frequency slots, while in NOMA, power domain separation is used to mitigate interference. This means that our Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) calculations are based on the assumption that interference is either negligible due to orthogonal resource allocation or is effectively managed through multiple access techniques.

The SINR at the u^{th} UAV due to the j^{th} GBS, denoted as $SINR_{j,u}$ is given by:

$$SINR_{j,u} = \frac{S_{j,u}}{I + P_{noise}} \quad (2)$$

where P_{noise} is the noise power and I is the interference power due to all GBSs except the j^{th} GBS. I is given by:

$$I = \sum_{i \neq j} S_{i,u} \quad (3)$$

Figure 1 One receiver and two transmitters in a 3D outdoor environment, showing the signal propagation paths between them.

where $S_{i,u}$ is the signal power at the u^{th} UAV due to the i^{th} GBS. Using different time-frequency resources or employing multiple access methods such as NOMA or OMA can mitigate or eliminate interference. In such cases, the interference term I would be significantly reduced or even negligible. We consider that the GBS with the greatest signal strength is chosen as the signal source of interest for the UAV. Thus, the SINR at the u^{th} UAV due to all GBSs, denoted as $SINR_u$ is given by:

$$SINR_u = \max_{1 \leq j \leq J} \{SINR_{j,u}\} \quad (4)$$

2.1 Ray Tracing Model

To calculate $SINR_u$, we need to compute $PL_{j,u}$ for each GBS-UAV pair. This can be done by using RT model either through SBR method or the image method^[18,26]. This model is suitable for computing propagation paths using 3D environment geometry^[17] for frequencies between 100 MHz to 100 GHz in an outdoor environment^[27]. The SBR method can be employed to model radio wave propagation in a 3D outdoor environment. Path loss calculations account for free-space loss, reflection losses, and diffraction losses^[28]. The model calculates losses for both horizontal and vertical polarizations for each reflection and diffraction by utilizing the Fresnel equation, Uniform Theory of Diffraction (UTD)^[29], geometric angle, and complex permittivity of materials ϵ_r ^[28].

The ITU-R P.2040-2^[30] recommendations include methods, equations, and values can be used to calculate ϵ_r of building materials for a range of frequencies. Equations to calculate complex permittivity values for Earth's surface are given in ITU-R P.527-6^[31]. Complex permittivity values for building materials ϵ_r can be calculated as follows^[31]:

$$\epsilon_r' = a f^b \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma = c f^d \quad (6)$$

$$\varepsilon_r = \varepsilon_r' + j \frac{\sigma}{2\pi\varepsilon_0 f} \quad (7)$$

where a,b,c and d are constants determined by the surface material, ε_r' is the relative permittivity, σ is the conductivity, ε_0 is the permittivity of free space and f is the frequency of the radio wave.

2.2 Federated Learning over UAVs (FL-UAVs)

During their flight, The UAVs form their local datasets $\mathcal{D}_u, \forall u$, based on the received signals from the GBSs. These datasets consist of pairs of input-output samples, with $n_u = |\mathcal{D}_u|, \forall u$. FL enables UAVs to collectively train a global model \boldsymbol{w} from their data without sharing it or the need to send it to a central server. The UAVs keep their data private, but they occasionally share their local model $\boldsymbol{w}_u, \forall u$ with a central server. In this study, the global model is assumed to be accessible to all GBSs.

The goal is to train a global model that minimizes the loss function $L(\boldsymbol{w})$ over the target distribution $\mathcal{D} = \bigcup_{u=1}^U \mathcal{D}_u$. We define $l_s(\boldsymbol{w})$ as the loss of the prediction on one data sample, e.g., mean square error. Thus, we can write the loss function as follows^[8]:

$$L(\boldsymbol{w}) = \sum_{u=1}^U \frac{n_u}{n} L_u(\boldsymbol{w}) \text{ where } L_u(\boldsymbol{w}) = \frac{1}{n_u} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{D}_u} l_s(\boldsymbol{w}) \quad (8)$$

where $n = \sum_{u=1}^U n_u$.

The GBSs initiate a training round r by broadcasting the global model \boldsymbol{w} of the previous training round to all UAVs. Each UAV updates their local model as $\boldsymbol{w}_u = \boldsymbol{w}, \forall u$ and takes E epochs of gradient decent on its local model using its local data. At each epoch, the local update is given by:

$$\boldsymbol{w}_u = \boldsymbol{w}_u - \eta \nabla L_u(\boldsymbol{w}_u) \quad (9)$$

where η is the learning rate and ∇ is the gradient operator. Then, each UAV uploads the updated local model of the current round to the GBSs, which aggregate local models to construct the global model \boldsymbol{w} . This process is repeated until reaching a predefined accuracy or a total number of rounds. Figure 2(a) shows the involved parties and illustrates the steps of the FL-UAVs process. Typically, for the first training round, the initial global model \boldsymbol{w}_0 is initialized randomly before broadcasting to all participants. This setup assumes that stable and frequent connections are maintained between the UAVs and the GBSs. However, we acknowledge that maintaining uninterrupted connections in real-world scenarios may pose challenges. Addressing these challenges could be a focus for future work.

The UAVs collect their local dataset randomly, which means that \mathcal{D} is not uniformly distributed among the UAVs. Thus, $\mathcal{D}_u, \forall u$ is non-IID and L_u could be an arbitrarily bad approximation to L ^[8]. FedAvg algorithm was proposed Ref. [8]

to solve (8) in non-IID setting. Thus, the GBSs aggregate the local models of all UAVs, using FedAvg algorithm, as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{w} = \sum_{u=1}^U \frac{n_u}{n} \boldsymbol{w}_u \quad (10)$$

In the FL-UAVs process, each training round incurs certain time and energy expenditures. The time expenditure arises because the UAV must first download the global model before it can begin its local training process. GBSs must then wait for all UAVs to complete their local training and send their local updates before they can aggregate these updates and initiate the next training round. Moreover, energy is consumed during the downloading of the global model, the local training process, and the uploading of the local updates back to the GBSs. Figure 2(b) presents the time and energy costs associated with a single training round of FL-UAVs.

Time Cost: We assume that the time cost for a UAV downloading the global model is negligible compared to uploading the local updates, as the GBSs are powerful components with limitless power sources. Let $t_u^{comm} = \frac{|\boldsymbol{w}_u|}{\mathcal{U}_u}$ be the time to upload the local update by u^{th} UAV, where \mathcal{U}_u is the data upload rate, and t_u^{epoch} be the time required to complete one epoch by u^{th} UAV, the time cost of one training round by u^{th} UAV is given as:

$$\mathcal{T}_u = t_u^{comm} + E t_u^{epoch} \quad (11)$$

We note that $|\boldsymbol{w}_u|$ is constant among all UAVs, this means that a UAV is a straggler if it has large data size or/and low computational capability, or its upload data rate is low. Thus, the time of one FL-UAVs round among all UAVs is equal to the time of the slowest UAV. Thus, we define the time cost of FL-UAVs as follows:

$$\mathcal{T} = \sum_{r=1}^R \max_{1 \leq u \leq U} \{\mathcal{T}_u\} \quad (12)$$

where R is the total number of training rounds.

Energy Cost: The energy consumption of uploading a local model by the u^{th} UAV is $e_u^{comm} = p_u t_u^{comm}$, where p_u is the transmission power of u^{th} UAV. Let e_u^{epoch} be the energy consumption of the u^{th} UAV for one epoch. Thus, the energy cost of FL-UAVs is given by:

$$\mathcal{E} = \sum_{r=1}^R \sum_{u=1}^U (p_u t_u^{comm} + E e_u^{epoch}) \quad (13)$$

We notice that, the time and energy complexity of FL-UAVs is $O(R)$. Consequently, reducing the total number of rounds required to achieve a specific performance level for the global model can effectively lower the computational and communication costs associated with FL-UAVs.

Figure 2 System model and overheads in FL-UAVs algorithm. (a) Parties involved and steps in the FL-UAVs process; (b) Time and energy costs in a single training round of FL-UAVs.

2.3 Performance Metrics

In the context of this research, certain metrics are employed to conduct a quantitative assessment of the SINR prediction outcomes. These metrics compute performance by comparing predicted data with real values to ascertain precision. The utilization of these metrics is imperative in determining the model that yields the highest performance.

The estimation of the models are regulated using Root mean squared error (RMSE) and R-squared (\mathcal{R}^2) metrics. Equations (14), (15) are used to compute RMSE and \mathcal{R}^2 values, respectively.

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2} \quad (14)$$

$$\mathcal{R}^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^m (Y_i - \bar{Y}_i)^2} \quad (15)$$

where m is the number of data points, Y_i denotes actual values, \hat{Y}_i denotes predicted values, and \bar{Y}_i denotes mean values.

3 Three-Step Approach for Coverage Prediction

The overall architecture of the proposed approach is depicted in Figure 3, that consists of RT simulation, pretraining, and fine-tuning steps. It necessitates the datasets of buildings and GBSs within the designated environment \mathcal{O} , in addition to the permittivity properties of buildings and terrain materials.

The dataset pertaining to the buildings includes their respective heights and spatial distribution within \mathcal{O} . The GBSs dataset contains the location, height, transmission power, and operating frequency of each GBS, in addition to their antenna azimuth and elevation angles. The outputs of the overall approach are the coverage prediction model and the evaluation metrics of both the pretraining and fine-tuning processes. The coverage prediction model is pretrained using an offline dataset, denoted as \mathcal{P} , and fine-tuned via FL-UAVs algorithm using the UAVs datasets, $\mathcal{D}_u, \forall u$. We provide details of the proposed approach steps in the following sections.

Figure 3 High level architecture of the proposed coverage prediction three-step approach for cellular-connected UAVs.

3.1 RT Simulation

The detailed procedure of the first step is shown in Figure 4. The process commences with the initialization of the transmitters array, derived from the GBSs dataset. The buildings dataset, in conjunction with the transmitters array, is utilized to construct a digital map. Subsequently, the propagation model is initialized, employing properties of buildings and terrain materials. The RT propagation model, which utilizes the SBR method with a maximum of two reflections and one diffraction per ray, is considered for this process. Following this, the spatial random sampling procedure is activated to randomly select $|\mathcal{P}|$ points, denoted as (x_p, y_p, H_p) , where $1 \leq p \leq |\mathcal{P}|$. The RT model then computes the path losses at the selected points, along with the SINR values to form the initial version of the offline dataset \mathcal{P} .

The generated simulation data is intrinsically linked to the global coordinate system. To mitigate this dependency, the simulation data is subsequently processed through the feature extraction stage. The vectors representing distance, azimuth, elevation, and LoS, denoted as \mathbf{d}_p , ϕ_p , θ_p , and \mathbf{l}_p respectively, are extracted from each data point p in \mathcal{P} . Assuming negligible error due to the Earth's curvature at the scale of the selected region, the Euclidean distance formula is employed to compute the distance between the p^{th} data point in \mathcal{P} and the j^{th} GBS, denoted as $d_{j,p}$, as follows:

$$d_{j,p} = \sqrt{(x_p - x_j)^2 + (y_p - y_j)^2 + (H_p - z_j)^2} \quad (16)$$

Consequently, the distance vector of the p^{th} data point in \mathcal{P} can be expressed as $\mathbf{d}_p = \{d_{j,p}, \forall j\}$. Similarly, we define the azimuth $\phi_p = \{\phi_{j,p}, \forall j\}$, elevation $\theta_p = \{\theta_{j,p}, \forall j\}$ and LoS $\mathbf{l}_p = \{\mathbf{l}_{j,p}, \forall j\}$ vectors. These vectors contain the azimuth angle $\phi_{j,p}$, elevation angle $\theta_{j,p}$, and LoS condition $\mathbf{l}_{j,p}$ of each GBS j with respect to the p^{th} data point in \mathcal{P} . The azimuth and elevation angles of the j^{th} GBS with respect to the p^{th} data point in \mathcal{P} are computed using the following formulas, respectively:

$$\phi_{j,p} = \arctan\left(\frac{y_p - y_j}{x_p - x_j}\right) \frac{180}{\pi} \quad (17)$$

$$\theta_{j,p} = \arctan\left(\frac{H_p - z_j}{\sqrt{(x_p - x_j)^2 + (y_p - y_j)^2}}\right) \frac{180}{\pi} \quad (18)$$

The \mathbf{l}_p vector is calculated using a simple LoS model that assumes a clear LoS path between the j^{th} GBS and p^{th} data point in \mathcal{P} if there are no obstacles between them.

$$\mathbf{l}_{j,p} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if no obstacles} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

Thus, the output of the RT simulation step is the offline dataset \mathcal{P} . Each data point in \mathcal{P} consists of the 3D location of a point in the environment, the SINR value at that point, and the four vectors from the feature extraction stage.

3.2 Pretraining Step and Model Design

Figure 5 delineates the pretraining process. It is a conventional process of training and validation of an ML model. Initially, the offline dataset undergoes preprocessing and is subsequently partitioned into training and testing subsets. Following this, the optimization of training hyperparameters is initiated. The Random Search algorithm^[32] is employed for the tuning of the hyperparameters. During each iteration, the initial ML model is trained on the training subset utilizing the hyperparameters sampled for the current iteration. Then, the pretrained model is validated using the testing subset. The pretrained model and the evaluation metrics from both the training and validation phases are preserved. Upon the conclusion of the pretraining process, the pretrained model exhibiting the most optimal performance, as determined by the collected metrics, is selected for use in the subsequent step.

Features Selection: This section discusses the various features present in the offline dataset, with the aim of identifying the most appropriate features for the training process. These features also have the potential to be computed by UAVs during their flight time. The 3D location is excluded from selection due to its dependency on the global coordinate system. However, we select the height $H_p, \forall p$ as it does not depend on the coordinate system. The \mathbf{l}_p vector is a viable candidate for the pretraining phase, but its computation by the UAVs is

Figure 4 Input, output and detailed procedure of the RT simulation step.

Figure 5 Pretraining step, including data preprocessing, hyperparameter tuning and model validation.

contingent on the availability of the digital map, which may not always be feasible.

The $\mathbf{d}_p, \phi_p, \theta_p$ vectors can be computed by the UAVs, provided the locations of the GBSs are made accessible to them. In the context of spatial analysis, these vectors inherently encapsulate information about the specific locations and quantity of the GBSs. Moreover, this dependency could potentially introduce bias into the training process. To counteract this, the preprocessing stage in the pretraining step transforms each raw vector into a vector of statistical metrics, thereby capturing the essential characteristics of the GBSs distribution. This effectively decouples the trained model from the specific GBSs locations and count. The transformation function is defined as follows:

$$T(\mathbf{V}) = [\mu_V, \text{median}_V, \sigma_V, \text{max}_V, \text{min}_V] \quad (20)$$

where μ_V represents the mean, median_V the median, σ_V the standard deviation, max_V the maximum value, and min_V the minimum of the vector \mathbf{V} . Thus, we define the vectors $\mathbf{d}'_p = T(\mathbf{d}_p), \forall p$, $\phi'_p = T(\phi_p), \forall p$, and $\theta'_p = T(\theta_p), \forall p$ as the selected features for the training process, in addition to $H_p, \forall p$.

Model Design: The initial model in the pretraining step could be any ML model that is suitable for regression problems, e.g., Linear Regression (LR) and Decision Tree (DT) models. For the purpose of this study, we propose a Dual Input Feature Fusion CNN (DIFF-CNN) model to be used to predict the SINR value. The proposed DIFF-CNN model consists of two one-dimensional convolutional layers followed by feature fusion through concatenation operation, layer normalization^[33], three fully connected layers and an output layer that contains one neuron. Figure 6 illustrates the structure of DIFF-CNN model. The first convolutional layer takes as input \mathbf{d}'_p, ϕ'_p , and θ'_p vectors, and applies κ filters of size 3. The second convolutional layer takes the κ -channel output from first layer and applies 2κ filters of size 3. After the convolution operations, the output is concatenated with H_p and normalized along the dimension of $2\kappa+1$. The normalized output is then flattened and passed through a series of three fully connected layers. The number of neurons in the first, second and third fully connected layers are v_1, v_2 , and v_3 , respectively. The convolutional and fully connected layers use ReLU activation function.

3.3 Fine-tuning via FL-UAVs

The pretrained model, denoted as $\omega_{\text{pretrained}}$, is derived from the pretraining step. Contrary to the conventional approach of random initialization of the initial global model ω_0 , the GBSs transmit $\omega_{\text{pretrained}}$ to the UAVs to initiate the fine-tuning step. It is assumed that the GBSs' dataset has already been dispatched to the UAVs. The fine-tuning step is outlined in Algorithm 1.

In each round, the current global model, ω , is broadcasted to all UAVs. Each UAV then executes the following steps in parallel:

1. The local dataset \mathcal{D}_u is updated by preprocessing the newly collected data to compute \mathbf{d}'_p, ϕ'_p , and θ'_p vectors using the GBSs's dataset and the equations (16), (17), (18) and (19), where p is a data point in the newly collected data by the UAV.
2. The dataset \mathcal{D}_u is partitioned into a training set, $\mathcal{D}_u^{\text{tr}}$, and validation set, $\mathcal{D}_u^{\text{va}}$.
3. The local validation metrics set, denoted as \mathcal{M}_u and comprising RMSE and \mathcal{R}^2 metrics, are computed by validating ω on $\mathcal{D}_u^{\text{va}}$.
4. The local model ω_u is set to the current global model ω .
5. For each epoch, the local model ω_u is updated on $\mathcal{D}_u^{\text{tr}}$ using the update rule defined in (9).
6. After E local epochs, the local model, ω_u , is transmitted to the GBSs, along with \mathcal{M}_u and the sizes of training and validation sets, $n_u = |\mathcal{D}_u^{\text{tr}}|$ and $n'_u = |\mathcal{D}_u^{\text{va}}|$.

Upon receipt of updates from all UAVs, the GBSs update the global model, ω , using (10). The global validation metrics set \mathcal{M} is also computed using the following averaging rule:

$$\mathcal{M}_i = \sum_{u=1}^U \frac{n'_u}{n'} \cdot \mathcal{M}_{u,i} \quad (21)$$

where $n' = \sum_{u=1}^U n'_u$, \mathcal{M}_i is the i^{th} metric in \mathcal{M} , and $\mathcal{M}_{u,i}$ is the i^{th} metric in \mathcal{M}_u . The training process is repeated until the number of rounds surpasses R . Ultimately, the algorithm yields the global model, ω . The transmission of the validation metrics $\mathcal{M}_u, \forall u$ along with n_u and n'_u is necessary to compute ω and \mathcal{M} . Furthermore, the transmission of these additional data along with the local model updates $\omega_u, \forall u$ does not alter the cost functions defined in (12) and (13) as they are of fixed sizes.

4 Validation and Comparison

4.1 Data Collection and Simulation Setup

To conduct this study, we developed a simulation environment representing a hypothetical 10×10 km urban-suburban area. This region features a randomized database of buildings, covering approximately 40% of the total area, while the remaining is open terrain. The majority of the buildings are less than 10m. The GBSs dataset consists of 18 transmitters, each located at specific ground points at a height of 10m and operating at a frequency f of 2.5 GHz. Figure 7 illustrates the distribution of buildings and the locations of the GBSs in the region.

Figure 6 Structure of the proposed DIFF-CNN model.

Algorithm 1 Fine-Tuning Algorithm using FL-UAVs

Require: $1 < E, 1 < R$

Ensure: ω

- 1: $r \leftarrow 1$
 - 2: $\omega \leftarrow \omega_{pretrained}$
 - 3: Broadcast GBSs dataset to the UAVs
 - 4: **repeat**
 - 5: Broadcast ω to the UAVs
 - 6: **for** each UAV u , where $1 \leq u \leq U$, **in parallel do**
 - 7: Update \mathcal{D}_u using newly collected data
 - 8: Split \mathcal{D}_u to \mathcal{D}_u^{tr} and \mathcal{D}_u^{va}
 - 9: Validate ω on \mathcal{D}_u^{va} to compute \mathcal{M}_u
 - 10: $\omega_u \leftarrow \omega$
 - 11: **for** $e = 1$ to E **do**
 - 12: Update ω_u on \mathcal{D}_u^{tr} using (9)
 - 13: **end for**
 - 14: $n_u \leftarrow |\mathcal{D}_u^{tr}|, n'_u \leftarrow |\mathcal{D}_u^{va}|$
 - 15: Upload $\{\omega_u, \mathcal{M}_u, n_u, n'_u\}$ to the GBSs
 - 16: **end for**
 - 17: Collect updates from all UAVs
 - 18: Update ω using (10)
 - 19: Compute \mathcal{M} using (21)
 - 20: $r \leftarrow r + 1$
 - 21: **until** $r > R$
-

The building in the region are primarily constructed from concrete. The relative permittivity ϵ_r was calculated using (7), where $\epsilon'_r = 5.31$ and $\sigma = 0.0684$ calculated using (5) and (6) respectively. The constants $a = 5.31$, $b = 0$, $c = 0.0326$ and $d = 0.8095$ where obtained from Table 3 Ref. [30]. The terrain material is vegetation, with ϵ_r calculated using the equations (51), (51) and (53) Ref. [31] for temperatures above zero.

The collected datasets were fed into the first step to collect

8×10^4 data points, constituting the offline dataset \mathcal{P} . Heights ranging between $20m$ and $300m$ were considered during the spatial random sampling procedure. The SINR values were computed using RT model. The vectors representing distance, azimuth, elevation, and LoS were computed for each data point and GBS pair using (16), (17), (18), and (19), respectively, during the feature extraction stage. Upon completion of the first step, the offline dataset was prepared for use in the pretraining step.

Four different ML models, namely, LR, K-Nearest Neighbors Regression (K-NN), DT and our proposed DIFF-CNN, were trained on \mathcal{P} during the pretraining step. The hyperparameters of each model were tuned to achieve optimal performance during the random search process of the pretraining step. Upon completion of the pretraining step, the resulting models and validation metrics were collected for subsequent

Figure 7 Distribution of buildings and ground base station locations in the simulated urban-suburban region.

analysis. The DIFF-CNN model exhibiting the highest performance was selected for use in the fine-tuning step.

Given the inaccessibility of measurement data and the high costs associated with validating the fine-tuning step in a real-world scenario, a simulation environment was established for the fine-tuning step. The FE2R model was used as a proxy for real-world measurements by the UAVs to collect the SINR values. Three different scenarios were considered to examine the impact of flying height on the fine-tuning process:

1. **Fixed H_u** Scenario: In this scenario, the altitude of all UAVs is the same, i.e., all UAVs fly at an altitude of $H_u = 100m$.
2. **Normal H_u** Scenario: In this scenario, the altitude of the UAVs follows a normal distribution, with a mean of $80m$ and a standard deviation of $10m$.
3. **Uniform H_u** Scenario: In this scenario, the altitude of the UAVs follows a uniform distribution, where $20m \leq H_u \leq 120m$.

In order to evaluate the efficiency of our proposed approach on the costs and performance of FL-UAVs, we conducted experiments under the three defined scenarios. In each scenario, the initial model, ω_0 , was initialized in two ways: randomly (denoted as *random* ω_0), as in the typical FL algorithm, and using the pretrained DIFF-CNN model (denoted as $\omega_0 = \omega_{pretrained}$).

Given that the time and energy cost is proportional to the number of training rounds, as demonstrated in (12) and (13), we introduced a measure, denoted as *Eff.*, to quantify the performance improvement gained by using $\omega_{pretrained}$ over random ω_0 . This measure is calculated as follows:

$$Eff. = \left(1 - \frac{R_{pretrained}}{R_{random}^*}\right) * 100 \quad (22)$$

In this equation, R_{random}^* represents the number of training rounds required to achieve the lowest RMSE over R rounds with *random* ω_0 . On the other hand, $R_{pretrained}$ represents the number of training rounds required to achieve the same or lower RMSE with $\omega_0 = \omega_{pretrained}$.

Furthermore, we varied the values of U and E to gain insights into their impact on the fine-tuning process. This analysis allows us to understand how the number of UAVs and the number of local epochs influence the efficiency and performance of our proposed approach in the context of FL-UAVs.

4.2 RT Simulation Results

An exploratory data analysis was performed on the dataset \mathcal{P} to understand its characteristics and identify any underlying patterns or trends. One of the key metrics computed was the probability of LoS, denoted as $Prob_{LoS,p}$, for each data

point p . This was calculated based on the \mathbf{t}_p vector as follows:

$$Prob_{LoS,p} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^J \mathbf{1}_{j,p}}{J} \quad (23)$$

Figure 8 illustrates a plot of $Prob_{LoS,p}$ values against distance at different heights. It is observed that $Prob_{LoS,p}$ decreases as the distance between the receiver and transmitter increases, irrespective of the receiver's height. This indicates that the likelihood of having a direct LoS between the receiver and transmitter diminishes as they become more distant from each other. However, the rate of decrease in $Prob_{LoS,p}$ is slower for higher receivers.

Figure 8 Comparative analysis of probability of LoS with respect to distance at different heights.

4.3 Pretraining Results

Table 1 provides a summary of the results from the pretraining step. The DIFF-CNN model outperforms the other models, achieving the lowest RMSE and the highest \mathcal{R}^2 values. The K-NN model follows closely, with performance metrics nearly equivalent to those of the DIFF-CNN model. The DT and LR models exhibit the least favorable performance. In addition, Table 1 presents the optimal hyperparameters for each model, as determined by the random search algorithm. For the DIFF-CNN model, these include the learning rate, mini-batch size, and the parameters κ , ν_1 , ν_2 , and ν_3 . For the K-NN model, the optimal number of neighbors is reported. For the DT model, the optimal maximum depth is provided. These hyperparameters were instrumental in achieving the best performance for each model.

In order to evaluate the generalization capabilities of the models under consideration for the prediction task, as well as their resilience to sparse data, these models were trained on a subset comprising 1% of the training set. The hyperparameters utilized in this process are detailed in Table 1. The RMSE

values for the models, when trained on both 1% and 100% of the training data, are depicted in Figure 9. Notably, the DIFF-CNN model demonstrates superior performance compared to the other models, even when the quantity of training data is limited.

Table 1 Evaluation metrics and optimal hyperparameters results of the pre-training step.

Model	RMSE	\mathcal{R}^2	Hyperparameters
LR	3.016	0.482	
K-NN	2.803	0.553	Number of Neighbors: 10
DT	3.231	0.529	Maximum Depth: 8
DIFF-CNN	2.762	0.566	Learning Rate: 0.001, Mini-batch Size: 1024, $\kappa=32$, $v_1=64$, $v_2=32$, $v_3=16$

Figure 9 Comparison of different ML models with respect to RMSE values and robustness to sparsity of training data.

4.4 Fine-tuning via FL-UAVs

The progression of the RMSE during the fine-tuning step for varying values of U and E is depicted in Figures 10 and 11. In all three scenarios, initializing ω_0 with $\omega_{pretrained}$ in Algorithm 1 results in a lower RMSE compared to a random initialization of ω_0 . This also leads to a quicker reduction in RMSE values, indicating a faster convergence of the global model. Among the scenarios, the *Fixed* H_u scenario outperforms the rest. This can be attributed to the absence of sparsity in their local datasets with respect to the altitude dimension, as all UAVs generate data points at the same altitude. On the other hand, the *Uniform* H_u scenario exhibits the highest error values, indicating a less performance.

Table 2 presents the numerical results of the fine-tuning step across various U values, with $E = 10$. For the *Fixed* H_u scenario, the global model attains an RMSE of 1.437 dB with $\omega_0 = \omega_{pretrained}$ and $U = 14$, representing a reduction of approximately 31% compared to the RMSE of 2.071 dB achieved with random ω_0 . A similar trend is observed for the *Normal* H_u scenario, with an error reduction of nearly 27%, and the *Uniform* H_u scenario, with an error reduction of around 20%, both at $U = 4$ and $U = 6$, respectively. Furthermore, the *Fixed* H_u and *Normal* H_u scenarios achieve an \mathcal{R}^2 performance of approximately 97%, while the *Uniform* H_u scenario yields an \mathcal{R}^2 performance of about 80%.

Table 3 summarizes the outcomes of the fine-tuning step across various E values, with $U = 10$. A comparison of the optimal performance results in both Table 2 and Table 3 reveals the following insights: For the *Fixed* H_u scenario, increasing E is more beneficial than increasing U . Specifically, the case with random ω_0 achieves an RMSE of 1.056 dB with $U = 10$ and $E = 50$, which is approximately 55% lower than the same case with $U = 18$ and $E = 10$. Similarly, the case with $\omega_0 = \omega_{pretrained}$ achieves an RMSE of 0.837 dB with $U = 10$ and $E = 50$, which is approximately 58% lower than the same case with $U = 14$ and $E = 10$. For both the *Normal* H_u and *Uniform* H_u scenarios, increasing E does not consistently lead to improved performance for both ω_0 and $\omega_0 = \omega_{pretrained}$ cases. However, the *Uniform* H_u scenario with $\omega_0 = \omega_{pretrained}$ achieves the lowest error of 3.161 dB for $E = 30$ and $U = 10$.

Impact of U : As depicted in Figure 12, the lowest RMSE values after $R = 200$ rounds are plotted for all U values. In the *Fixed* H_u scenario, the performance of the global model remains unaffected by an increase in the number of UAVs. However, in other scenarios, a slight increase in error values is observed with an increase in U . Notably, for all U values, the performance across all scenarios is superior when $\omega_0 = \omega_{pretrained}$ is used instead of a random initialization for ω_0 .

Impact of E : Figure 13 presents the lowest RMSE values after $R = 200$ rounds for different E values. In the *Fixed* H_u scenario, an increase in E results in a decrease in RMSE values for both $\omega_0 = \omega_{pretrained}$ and random ω_0 cases, with the former exhibiting superior performance. Conversely, in both the *Normal* H_u and *Uniform* H_u scenarios, extremely low or high E values lead to an increase in error, with the latter scenario performing worse. Nevertheless, the use of the pre-trained model consistently results in better performance than random ω_0 initialization across all scenarios.

Efficiency of the Proposed Approach: In order to measure the efficiency of the proposed approach for different scenarios and across all of considered U and E values, R_{random}^* and $R_{pretrained}$ were identified and $Eff.$ was calculated using (22). Figure 14 plots R_{random}^* , $R_{pretrained}$ and $Eff.$ across all U values. We can notice that, for all scenarios and for almost all U

Figure 10 RMSE progression during the fine-tuning step across different U values, where $E = 10$ and $R = 200$.

Figure 11 RMSE progression during the fine-tuning step across different E values, where $U = 10$ and $R = 200$.

Table 2 Achieved RMSE and \mathcal{R}^2 for different values of U w.r.t the UAVs height distribution and ω_0 , where $E = 10$ and $R = 200$.

H_u	ω_0	\mathcal{M}_i	$U=2$	$U=4$	$U=6$	$U=8$	$U=10$	$U=12$	$U=14$	$U=16$	$U=18$	$U=20$
<i>Fixed</i>	random	RMSE	2.059	2.009	2.090	1.983	2.044	1.995	2.071	2.172	1.899	2.100
		\mathcal{R}^2	0.920	0.901	0.909	0.914	0.913	0.919	0.916	0.903	0.912	0.905
	$\omega_{pretrained}$	RMSE	1.543	1.596	1.467	1.480	1.468	1.512	1.437	1.471	1.485	1.498
		\mathcal{R}^2	0.971	0.959	0.973	0.962	0.954	0.956	0.970	0.960	0.951	0.973
<i>Normal</i>	random	RMSE	2.389	2.378	2.999	4.641	3.876	3.072	3.432	3.251	3.389	3.467
		\mathcal{R}^2	0.902	0.897	0.886	0.803	0.841	0.882	0.867	0.872	0.856	0.860
	$\omega_{pretrained}$	RMSE	1.803	1.744	2.026	2.269	2.384	2.006	2.748	1.930	2.658	2.705
		\mathcal{R}^2	0.968	0.969	0.959	0.849	0.931	0.914	0.928	0.953	0.925	0.927
<i>Uniform</i>	random	RMSE	9.379	6.253	6.340	7.354	7.339	8.297	7.528	7.644	7.166	7.796
		\mathcal{R}^2	0.368	0.668	0.632	0.533	0.551	0.444	0.508	0.494	0.550	0.491
	$\omega_{pretrained}$	RMSE	7.034	4.988	4.846	5.837	6.107	6.256	5.955	5.938	5.966	6.142
		\mathcal{R}^2	0.544	0.806	0.735	0.671	0.679	0.662	0.649	0.592	0.654	0.659

values, R_{random}^* is equal to $R = 200$ rounds. which indicates that the performance of the global model keeps improving. $R_{pretrained}^*$ is always lower than R_{random}^* . The efficiency is vary depending of the scenario and U value. However, we can see that, the efficiency in *Fixed* H_u scenario is between 40% and 60%, in the *Normal* H_u scenario is between 60% and 90%, and *Uniform* H_u scenario is above 90%.

Figure 15 plots R_{random}^* , $R_{pretrained}^*$ and $Eff.$ across all E values. The same notes from the Figure 14 are noted also. However, we can see that, the efficiency in *Fixed* H_u scenario is between 35% and 70%, in the *Normal* H_u scenario is be-

tween 70% and 90%, and *Uniform* H_u scenario is above 90%.

5 Discussion

The RT simulation results offered critical insights into the relationship between the probability of LoS, distance, and receiver height. As anticipated, an increase in distance between the receiver and transmitter generally led to a decrease in the probability of a direct LoS. This is likely due to the increased likelihood of obstructions and interference at greater

Table 3 Achieved RMSE and \mathcal{R}^2 for different values of E w.r.t the UAVs height distribution and ω_0 , where $U = 10$ and $R = 200$.

H_u	ω_0	\mathcal{M}_i	$E = 5$	$E = 10$	$E = 20$	$E = 30$	$E = 40$	$E = 50$
<i>Fixed</i>	random	RMSE	3.017	2.044	1.594	1.234	1.091	1.056
		\mathcal{R}^2	0.838	0.913	0.944	0.958	0.967	0.964
	$\omega_{pretrained}$	RMSE	1.917	1.468	1.114	0.978	0.852	0.837
		\mathcal{R}^2	0.958	0.954	0.933	0.977	0.977	0.977
<i>Normal</i>	random	RMSE	4.702	3.876	3.730	2.944	2.984	3.728
		\mathcal{R}^2	0.772	0.841	0.905	0.907	0.904	0.860
	$\omega_{pretrained}$	RMSE	2.905	2.384	2.805	2.405	2.444	2.308
		\mathcal{R}^2	0.913	0.931	0.924	0.943	0.931	0.938
<i>Uniform</i>	random	RMSE	8.278	7.339	6.800	8.687	9.293	8.255
		\mathcal{R}^2	0.437	0.551	0.587	0.369	0.204	0.295
	$\omega_{pretrained}$	RMSE	6.405	6.107	5.185	3.161	7.627	7.481
		\mathcal{R}^2	0.635	0.679	0.682	0.888	0.378	0.474

Figure 13 Impact of E on the achieved RMSE.

distances. Interestingly, the study found that the rate of decrease in the probability of LoS was slower for receivers at

higher altitudes. This suggests that at higher altitudes, UAVs may maintain a higher probability of LoS over larger distances.

The pretraining results underscored the robust performance of the proposed DIFF-CNN model in comparison to other machine learning models. The DIFF-CNN model demonstrated superior predictive capabilities and a strong fit to the training data. Notably, the model maintained this high level of performance even when trained on a limited dataset comprising just 1% of the total training set. This suggests that the DIFF-CNN model could be particularly effective in real-world scenarios where data may be limited or costly to obtain. Interestingly, the K-NN model also performed well. This suggests that simple, distance-based models can still be effective for SINR prediction task. However, it's worth noting that the performance of the K-NN model decreased notably when the size of the training data was reduced. In contrast, the DT and LR models were found to be less suitable for the SINR prediction task.

The fine-tuning results underscored the significant impact of UAVs flying heights on the performance of the global model. When all UAVs flew at the same altitude, the model achieved an RMSE of 0.837 dB and an \mathcal{R}^2 of 97.7%, as shown in Table 3. However, increasing the distribution of flying heights led to a decrease in model performance, likely due to increased sparsity of collected data with respect to the height dimension. Specifically, the model achieved an RMSE of 1.744 dB and an \mathcal{R}^2 of 96.9% for a normal distribution of flying heights, as shown in Table 2, and an RMSE of an 3.161 dB and \mathcal{R}^2 of 88.8% for a uniform distribution, as shown in Table 3.

The study also explored the impact of the number of UAVs and local epochs on the fine-tuning process. In scenarios where all UAVs flew at the same altitude, the number of UAVs did not affect the model performance, but increasing the number of local epochs could improved the model performance. However, in scenarios with different flying heights, increas-

Figure 14 Efficiency of the proposed approach with respect to different U values.

Figure 15 Efficiency of the proposed approach with respect to different E values.

ing the number of UAVs decreased the model performance, due to an increase in data sparsity. Additionally, setting the local epochs too low or too high also led to a decrease in model performance, likely due over-fitting phenomena.

Importantly, the results demonstrated the effectiveness of the proposed approach of using the pretrained model on RT simulation data as a starting point for the FL-UAVs algorithm. Despite variations in UAVs flying altitude, this approach led to better performance. Moreover, it effectively reduced the time and energy costs introduced by the FL-UAVs algorithm. The results showed that using this approach, a reduction in the number of training rounds from 35% up to 70% could be achieved for the fixed altitude scenario, and above 90% for the uniformly distributed height scenario. The difference in efficiency is because the pretrained model was trained on a dataset that contains data points at different heights. This leads to more rounds to fine-tune the pretrained model in the fixed altitude scenario. On the other hand, for other scenarios, it takes fewer rounds to be fine-tuned. This suggests that using different pretrained models for different scenarios, depending on the flying height, may lead to high efficiency for all scenarios. This can be a subject for future research.

6 Conclusion

This research addressed the challenge of predicting the SINR for cellular-connected UAVs. We developed a cost-effective approach that combines RT method, deep learning, and FL to enhance UAV signal quality prediction, considering practical constraints and privacy considerations. The problem lies in ensuring reliable communication for UAVs in diverse environments due to factors such as LoS probability and UAV flying height. Our solution is a three-step approach: RT simulation for computing signal propagation paths, pre-training proposed DIFF-CNN model on derived dataset from RT data, and fine-tuning the pretrained model using FL with data collected by each UAV during flight. Our approach has demonstrated superior performance with an RMSE of 0.837 dB and \mathcal{R}^2 of 97.7% for SINR prediction after fine-tuning in the fixed-altitude scenario, and efficiency gains by reducing training rounds by 35% to 90%.

A key takeaway from this research is the potential efficiency gains achieved by using different pretrained models based on specific flying heights. Moreover, while the proposed approach is particularly effective for UAV scenarios, it is not limited to UAVs alone. Any device capable of collecting

data on signal quality can participate in the training process, including fixed or mobile IoT devices deployed in the target environment. Future work could address the extension of our approach to heterogeneous devices, where device participation in the learning process can be based on available energy and computational power

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